

Research Article

Availability and Utilization of Instructional Resources for Entrepreneurship in Business Education in Colleges of Education

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Abstract: The study was necessitated by the declining success of colleges of education in South-East Nigeria in producing business education graduates with requisite knowledge, skills and competencies through entrepreneurship education that depends on the effective utilization of relevant instructional resources. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent to which instructional resources are available and being utilized for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted 132 business educators from seven colleges of education in the area. The entire population was used without sample size because the population was manageable. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with five-point rating scale which contained 20-items. The instrument was validated by three experts. A pilot test was used to establish the reliability of the instrument and data collected were analyzed using Cronbach alpha to obtained reliability coefficient values of 0.79 and 0.84 with an overall coefficient value of 0.82. Frequency count, percentages, Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while chi-square and t-test were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that physical facilities were not adequately available for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. Gender did not significantly influence the level of utilization of available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education. Based on the findings, it was concluded that level of availability and utilization of instructional resources for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria is not adequate for equipping students for entrepreneurial success on graduation. It was therefore, recommended among others, that administrators of colleges of education in South-East Nigeria should be encouraged to undertake fund raising activities, the funds of which should be judiciously used to procure adequate physical facilities and equipment to enhance effective teaching of entrepreneurship in business education.

Keywords: Availability, Utilization, Instructional Resources, Entrepreneurship, Business Education.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship education is a form of education that seeks to provide knowledge, skills, attitude and motivation to students for entrepreneurial success in any setting. It equips people with the ability to seek investment opportunities (Azonuche and Umerri, 2012). Entrepreneurship education inculcates in individuals entrepreneurial skills that enable them to confront situations in creative and innovative ways (Chiaha and Agu, 2013). Chiaha and Agu (2013) further explained that entrepreneurial individuals create jobs for themselves and others thereby reducing unemployment. Even when such individuals are employed by other enterprises, they are known as entrepreneurs who

become agents of business expansion and growth leading to the creation of more business opportunities and more jobs.

From the foregoing, entrepreneurship education is an educational programme that is designed to equip students with necessary skills and competencies for successful establishment and operation of business ventures. Such skills include opportunity recognition, creativity, innovation and risk taking as well as the ability to plan and manage businesses in order to achieve desirable goals. Ordu and Abdulkarim (2016) noted that entrepreneurship education is offered in colleges of education both as a general course and departmental courses especially in business education.

One of the objectives of tertiary institutions (including colleges of education) is the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society. Unfortunately, the possession of various degrees and certificates from tertiary institutions is no longer a guarantee for employment. Many young graduates continue to roam the streets in search of white-collar jobs which are almost not in existence. This has led to a general feeling of despondency among the graduates (Inibehe and Dankaro, 2012).

Ile, Nwogu and Ogudionye (2015) noted that the causes of high rate of unemployment among Nigerian graduates are of two-folds. The first, according to the Ile, Nwogu and Ogudionye (2015) is the obvious lack of employment opportunities in the country. The second is that the graduates are deficient in terms of the necessary skills and competencies required for employment in contemporary business organizations, hence they are more or less unemployable. Additionally, the huge number of youths graduating from various tertiary institutions each year further worsens the situation as the available industries are incapable of absorbing most of them considering the present unemployment in the country.

To reverse this ugly trend, especially as it affects graduate unemployment, the government of Nigeria in 2006 introduced entrepreneurial education as a compulsory course in tertiary institutions with the aim of preparing graduates for entrepreneurial success through private sector initiative (Agbonlahor, 2016). This was based on the notion that tertiary institutions should change their orientation as mills for job seekers rather than job creators. According to Agbonlahor (2016), this initiative was to serve as the flagship to drive economic and social reconstruction against the backdrop of youth unemployment and the thousands of school leavers every year. Ojiefu (2012) reported that the rising graduate unemployment and the low entrepreneurial drive among school leavers in Nigeria led to the repositioning of tertiary institutions as centers for building self-sustaining graduates that will be future captains of industries.

One of the measures taken by the government to reposition tertiary institutions towards producing self-sustaining graduates is the introduction of entrepreneurship education into the curriculum of all tertiary institutions including colleges of education. Accordingly, Ordu (2012) reported that the introduction of entrepreneurship in tertiary education curriculum was followed by the directive from government in 2007 that all tertiary institutions should establish Centres for Entrepreneurship Development (CED). Ordu further explained that the directive was given so that the Centres (CEDs) would co-ordinate teaching and learning of entrepreneurship education to achieve government objectives.

Business education is one of the programmes in colleges of education with entrepreneurial courses in the content. It is an educational programme designed to equip young people with necessary skills and competencies that would enable them engage in skill acquisition and productive livelihoods (Ezeani, 2014). In other words, business education, a component of vocational education, is said to be a set of instructions offered to prepare students for jobs in the business world (Nzerem in Barakabo and Eze, 2016). According to Udoh (2010), business education is a means by which an individual develops understanding and skills to be able to enter into the business world and become self-reliant.

In view of the importance of business education in skills development, the graduates of the programme are expected to venture into various entrepreneurial activities upon graduation. It is against this background that entrepreneurship education was integrated into the curriculum of business education programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Ezeani, 2014). The aim of this is to ensure that the students, upon graduation, acquire the necessary skills, knowledge and competencies to enable them successfully set up and manage their own businesses. This will help reduce the high rate of poverty, create employment opportunities and reduce rural-urban migration. Business education programme offers graduates of colleges of education adequate training in risk management to enable them to be creative and innovative in identifying novel business opportunities (Ugwoke, Basake, Diara and Chukwuma, 2014). However, the teaching and learning of entrepreneurial courses in business education programme in colleges of education in Nigeria is facing challenges due to lack of adequate instructional resources (Amesi and Giami, 2018).

Instructional resources are all the tools which are needed by the teacher to provide help and encouragement to pupils' learning activities (Ema & Ajayi in Chukwu, Eze and Agada, 2016). In the words of Onyejemezi in Eya and Ureme (2011), instructional resources are materials or teaching materials, which a teacher utilizes in the course of presenting a lesson in order to make the content of the lesson understandable to the learners. The implication is that the use of instructional resources is inevitable if effective teaching and learning must be achieved. Instructional resources range from homemade devices to sophisticated machines and also people who assist the teacher in disseminating knowledge and information to help learners learn meaningfully (Shamsuddin, Arome and Aminu, 2018).

Ogundele (2011) outlined examples of instructional resources in entrepreneurship education to include equipment, computer facilities, entrepreneurship textbooks, tools, farm lands, learning/instructional materials, consumable materials and infrastructure (classrooms, lecture theatres, libraries, laboratories and workshops). According to Onyesom and Okolocha (2013), instructional resources in business education which could also be applicable to entrepreneurship education include business educators (teachers), typewriting laboratories, shorthand studios, model offices, facilities such as classroom, library as well as equipment such as computers, typewriters among others.

It is necessary to add that apart from physical facilities, equipment and personnel, instructional resources in entrepreneurship programme also include non-book materials such as time (period allocated for the programme), machines used for teaching, programmed materials, motion pictures and films, video tape recording, audio tape recording, facilities such as space, online materials, films/videos/CDS, open source materials and video collection (Ordu and Abdulkarim, 2016).

It is also important to note that all instructional resources listed above are found within an educational institution which has the mandate to teach entrepreneurship, the availability and utilization of the items may not be far from the realities of training. This is why the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) always carries out accreditation exercise in institutions to ensure that the standard is maintained.

Amakaino and Chamberlain (2013) explained that the minimum standards describe standards as they relate to quality which constitutes the yardstick for the assessment of values and comparability, interpretability and harmonization. The idea of setting minimum standards or benchmark involves developing criteria or yardsticks for comparing what is obtainable against what ought to be. It is the process of identifying and learning from good practices in other organizations by regularly comparing aspects of performance, identifying gaps in performance and seeking fresh approaches to bringing improvements in the performance (Amakaino and Chamberlain, 2013). The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2012) classified resources in business education into three namely physical facilities, equipment and personnel. Thus, this study deal with physical

facilities available and being utilized for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. The physical facilities include classroom blocks, workshops, laboratories/studios, libraries and staff offices, entrepreneurship garden, mentor's shops and/or work places, community business enterprises. This instructional resources need to be available and fully utilized to enhance effective teaching and learning in entrepreneurship business education.

According to Joseph and Philiias (2011), availability is a characteristic of a resource that is committable, operable, or usable upon demand to perform its designated or required functions. To enhance effective teaching and learning for entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education, there is need for provision of adequate instructional resources. Joseph and Phillias (2011) noted further that there is low or inadequate provision of physical facilities in schools would inhibit students' academic performance. However, it appears that the inadequacy of instructional resources for entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education is affecting effective teaching and learning. Thus, the extent instructional resources are utilized in the business education programme will; to a large extent depend on their availability.

Utilization is the art of putting things or resources that are tangible or intangible to proper use. The term utilization refers to the employment of any tool or services that will facilitate performance (Nwazor and Udegbunam, 2016). Utilization of resources connotes the equitable use of resources of an enterprise especially education industry for effective implementation of the curriculum. Utilization of instructional resources in entrepreneurship business education requires teachers' knowledge in the subject area and understanding how students learn using varied instructional resources as well as good level of technical expertise (Fan, 2011). Nwankwo, Nwogbo, Okorji and Egboka (2015) reported that learning facilities for implementing the entrepreneurship education programme in the State were inadequate and low level of utilization of learning facilities in entrepreneurship education.

One influencing factor in the context of availability and utilization of instructional resources is gender. Gender is factor that could influence the utilization of instructional resources for teaching among business educators. Nwazor and Udegbunam (2016) reported that gender could be a factor in low teacher utilization of resources for instructional delivery. It is obvious that the success of colleges of education in South-East Nigeria in producing business education graduates with requisite knowledge, skills and competencies through entrepreneurship education depends on the availability and effective utilization of relevant instructional resources. It is against this background that this study sought to determine the availability and utilization of instructional resources for entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria is undertaken.

Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurship education is an educational process that is geared towards equipping students with creative and innovative ideas for self-employment and job creation. In order to achieve these objectives, instructional resources are to be adequately available and utilized to facilitate effective teaching and learning. Entrepreneurship business education being skill-based requires ample availability of instructional resources such as personnel, equipment and facilities as well as well-equipped laboratories and workshops for student practice exercises. However, it is widely reported that this laudable programme in Nigerian institutions faces enormous challenges due to lack of relevant instructional resources (Ogundele, 2011).

The problem of this study therefore is that availability and utilization of instructional resources for entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria is not clearly known. If the status is not determined through an empirical study such as this, relevant stakeholders may not take objective measures to ensure that the graduates are suitably empowered to succeed in self-employment and job creation.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the extent to which instructional resources are available and being utilized for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined the:

- 1) Physical facilities available for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.
- 2) Available physical facilities utilization for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- 1) What physical facilities are available for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria?
- 2) To what extent are the available physical facilities utilized by lecturers' for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

- 1) There is no significant difference in the percentage ratings of male and female respondents on the available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.
- 2) Male and female respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the level of utilization of available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 132 business educators from seven colleges of education owned by government in South-East Nigeria where entrepreneurship education is being run as a course in the business education programme. No sample size was used for the study. The instrument used Checklist on Availability of Instructional Resources and Observational Guide was also used on Utilization. The structured observational guide used was on a five-point rating scale with response categories as very highly utilized (VHU), highly utilized (HU), moderately utilized (MU), lowly utilized (LU) and very lowly utilized (VLU). Three experts validated the instrument, one in the field of business education and one expert in measurement and evaluation, from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. A pilot test was used to establish the reliability of the instrument by administering it to twenty business educators from colleges of education-Agbor, Delta State Nigeria was used, which is outside the study area but have similar features to the studied area. The computation of data collected was analyzed using Cronbach alpha to ensure the internal consistency and obtained an overall coefficient value of 0.82.

Copies of the questionnaire instrument were administered to the respondents by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who were briefed on how to administer the instrument. The researcher or an assistant agreed and hand over copies of the instruments to the Head of Department with a plan to assist in distributing them to the lectures and returned as agreed to retrieve completed copies. This procedure facilitated careful completion of the instrument and a high response rate of business educators' observation. Out of the 132 copies of the observational guide giving to the business educators, 128 copies (representing 97 percent) were retrieved with an attrition rate of eight copies (representing 3 percent) and used for data analysis. Data collected were analysed using frequency count and percentages for research question 1 that any item with 50 percent and above is considering available and below 50 percent is consider not available while mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question 2 to determine the closeness of the respondents' means. In testing the null hypotheses, chi-square was used to test hypothesis 1 on availability, while

t-test was used to test the null hypothesis 2 at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the calculated p-value is less than the stipulated level of significance (0.05), it meant that there was a significant difference and the hypothesis is rejected. Conversely, where the calculated p-value is equal to or greater than the stipulated level of significance (0.05), it meant that there was no significant difference and the hypothesis was not rejected.

Result

Research Question 1

What physical facilities are available for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria?

Table 1. Percentage scores on availability of physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

S/N	Items on Physical facilities	Available		Not available		Decision
		Freq	%	Freq	%	
1	Classroom blocks	53	74.22	33	25.78	Available
2	Workshops	51	89.84	13	10.16	Available
3	Laboratories/studios	11	76.56	30	23.44	Available
4	Departmental libraries	55	18.75	104	81.25	Not Available
5	Staff offices	50	84.38	20	15.62	Available
6	Entrepreneurship garden	16	13.28	111	86.72	Not Available
7	Mentor’s shop/workplaces	14	21.88	100	78.12	Not Available
8	Community business centres	3	82.03	23	17.97	Available
9	Farm lands	13	12.50	112	85.50	Not Available
10	Typing pool	52	13.28	111	86.72	Not Available
Cluster %			48.67		51.33	

Data in Table 1 shows that only five of the 10 physical facilities listed are available while the rest are not available for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. The cluster percentage shows that physical facilities are not available with percentage score of 51.33 against the available with percentage score of 48.67.

Research Question 2

What is the level of lecturers’ utilization of physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria?

Table 2. Respondents’ mean ratings on the level of utilization of physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

S/N	Items on level of utilization of physical facilities	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Classroom blocks	3.45	0.70	Moderately Utilized
2	Workshops	3.20	0.54	Moderately Utilized
3	Laboratories/studios	3.75	0.46	Highly Utilized
4	Departmental libraries	2.20	0.40	Lowly Utilized
5	Staff offices	3.57	0.45	Highly Utilized
6	Entrepreneurship garden	1.87	0.45	Not Utilized
7	Mentor’s shop/workplaces	2.25	0.40	Lowly Utilized
8	Community business centres	2.56	0.75	Moderately Utilized
9	Farm lands	2.42	0.70	Lowly Utilized
10	Typing pool	1.45	0.83	Not Utilized
Cluster Mean		2.64		Moderately Utilized

Data in Table 2 shows that in the item by item analysis, only two items have mean scores ranged of 3.57 and 3.75 indicating that respondents highly utilized the physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship. Three items have mean scores ranging from 2.56 to 3.45 showing that the respondents moderately utilized but were lowly utilized in three items also with mean scores ranging from 2.20 to 2.45.

The remaining two items were not utilized with mean scores ranged of 1.45 and 1.87. However, that the cluster mean score is 2.64 which indicate that physical facilities are moderately utilized for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. The standard deviation for all the items falls between 0.40 to 0.83 which indicates that respondents are not wide apart in their views.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the percentage ratings of male and female respondents on the available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

Table 3. Chi-square analysis on the percentage ratings of male and female respondents on the available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

S/N	Available Physical facilities	Male (n=57)				Female (n=71)				X ²	P-value	Remarks
		Available		Not Available		Available		Not Available				
		Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%			
1	Classroom Blocks	53	93.0	4	7.0	68	95.8	3	4.2	.04	.80	Not Sig
2	Workshops	51	89.5	6	10.5	66	93.0	5	7.0	11.67	.00	Sig
3	Laboratories/studios	11	19.3	46	80.7	58	81.7	13	18.3	.19	.46	Not Sig
4	Departmental Libraries	55	96.5	2	3.5	60	84.5	11	15.5	14.82	.00	Sig
5	Staff Offices	50	87.7	7	12.3	30	42.3	41	57.7	5.93	.01	Sig
6	Entrepreneurship garden	16	28.1	41	71.9	21	29.6	50	70.4	.64	.15	Not Sig
7	Mentor's shop/workplaces	14	24.6	43	75.4	9	12.7	62	87.3	23.34	.00	Sig
8	Community Business Centres	3	5.3	54	94.7	18	25.4	53	74.6	.01	.53	Not Sig
9	Farm Land	13	22.8	44	77.2	28	39.4	43	60.6	1.68	.11	Not Sig
10	Typing Pool	52	91.2	5	8.8	10	14.1	61	85.9	2.99	.10	Not Sig

The analysis in Table 3 shows that six out of the 10 listed items had p-value greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the percentage ratings of male and female respondents on the available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Hypothesis Two

Male and female respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the level of utilization of available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

Table 4. Summary of t-test result of male and female respondents' mean ratings on the level of utilization of available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	α	df	t-cal	p-value	Decision
Male	57	3.62	1.17	0.05	126	.93	.35	Not Significant
Female	71	3.10	1.21					

Data in Table 4 shows that the calculated t-value is .93 at 126 degree of freedom and .35 p-value. Since the p-value is greater than the significant value (0.05), it means that male and female respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the level of utilization of available physical facilities for entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. The null hypothesis was, therefore not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study revealed that physical facilities are not adequately available for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. The finding is also in agreement with Joseph and Phillias (2011) who reported that there is low or inadequate provision of physical facilities in schools would inhibit students' academic performance. Thus, there is need for government and other relevant stakeholders in education in Nigeria to ensure that physical facilities are made available enough so as to enhance effective teaching and learning in the school system. The test of the first hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference in the percentage ratings responses of male and female; and federal and state owned institutions respondents on the available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

The findings of the study on utilization of available physical facilities revealed that there are moderately utilized for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. The finding is in consonance with Nwankwo, Nwogbo, Okorji and Egboka (2015) who reported that learning facilities for implementing the entrepreneurship education programme in the State were inadequate and low level of utilization of learning facilities in entrepreneurship education. The test of the second hypothesis also revealed that male and female respondents did not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the level of utilization of available physical facilities for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria. The findings is line with Nwazor and Udegbunam (2016) who reported that gender could be a factor in low teacher utilization of resources for instructional delivery.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that level of availability and utilization of instructional resources for teaching entrepreneurship in business education in colleges of education in South-East Nigeria is not adequate for equipping students for entrepreneurial success on graduation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1) Administrators of colleges of education in South-East Nigeria should be encouraged to undertake fund raising activities, the funds of which should be judiciously used to procure adequate physical facilities to enhance effective teaching of entrepreneurship in business education.
- 2) There should be training programmes and skill development for business education lecturers that will encourage them to have the requisite skills, competences and exposure to enable them to be more proficient in the utilization of physical facilities in teaching/learning of entrepreneurship course contents.

Conflicts of interest: There is no conflict of interest of any kind.

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